

PRIMARY NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASES DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF PREVENTION AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF COMORBIDITY

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The purpose of the study was to study and evaluate the characteristics of the prevention of the main non-communicable diseases (NCDs) in the ecological, geographical and climatic conditions of the valley against the background of comorbidity (CF).

Research methods and materials. In the conditions of the valley, special methods of tetroanalysis of the results of epidemiological studies conducted in different years and prevention are used (retrospective epidemiological analysis, instrumental and survey analysis). 1323 surveys of the working age population were statistically analyzed and evaluated.

Obtained results and conclusions. The ecological and climatic conditions of the valley are considered as a risk factor for CKD, and this has been proven in regional studies. According to our analysis, one more scientific conclusion is confirmed: the tendency to identify a large number of AYuBK (comorbidity) in the valley conditions is observed at the population level. It was found that the prevalence of comorbidity is 86%, and CF is not recorded in only 14% of the population ($R < 0.01$). It is also confirmed that this epidemiological situation is typical for almost all age groups. In particular, it is confirmed that 43.0% of people under the age of 20 will pass AYUBK with CF, 76.2% at the age of 20-29, 94.7% at the age of 30-39, and 98.6% at the age of 40-49. Binary CF (84.7 percent), "Triple CF" (83.0 percent), "Quadruple CF" (57.9 percent) and "Five CF" (41.8 percent) are observed.

Conclusions: 1) Preventive measures of CKD should have different aspects in the conditions of the valley, such as the background of comorbidity should be taken into account. 2) If pharmacotherapeutic treatment is strengthened in secondary and tertiary prevention programs, and non-pharmacological methods (mainly by promoting and applying folk medicine) are improved in the primary prevention of CKD by taking into account comorbidity indices, or if research in this direction is strengthened, it will be appropriate in the conditions of the valley.

